

SOCIAL SCIENCES

LIVING MOSAIC: CULTURAL RIGHTS IN CONSTANT EVOLUTION

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Abstract

This study focused on analyzing the dynamic interrelationship between Mexican cultural diversity and the effectiveness of the application of human rights in the contemporary context. Using a mixed methodology, the way in which diverse cultural worldviews interact with current regulatory frameworks was investigated. The empirical results reveal a complex interdependence, where cultural diversity, especially linguistic diversity, enriches the understanding and exercise of human rights. It was also observed that cultural diversity promotes new forms of citizen participation and a deeper understanding of human rights. However, they also underline the urgent need for public policies designed to recognize and respect cultural plurality, adapting to local particularities and fostering intercultural dialogue. In conclusion, this study emphasizes the importance of integrating cultural diversity as a fundamental element in the effective guarantee of human rights in the Mexican context, as well as examining the effectiveness of public policies implemented to promote inclusion and respect for diversity.

Keywords: cultural diversity, Mexico, human rights, citizenship

Introduction.

Mexico is a living country, a mosaic in constant transformation. Just as the pieces of a mosaic come together to form a beautiful and complex whole, the diverse cultures that coexist in this country intertwine to create a rich social tapestry. However, this living mosaic is constantly evolving, and with it, the challenges to guarantee the cultural rights of all its members. With this in mind, we propose to identify the main challenges and opportunities that arise from the intersection between cultural diversity and human rights in Mexico and analyze how the cultural norms, values, and practices of different cultural groups influence the perception and exercise of human rights.

Berenzon (2023) Cultural diversity is a fundamental characteristic of Mexico. The presence of more than 60 indigenous and Afro-descendant peoples, who speak more than 11 linguistic families, enriches the country's cultural heritage. It is important to recognize and value the contribution of these groups to Mexican history, society and culture, as well as the challenges they face in terms of rights and development. "In Mexico, 10% of the population belongs to an indigenous people, which is equivalent to twelve million people. Similarly, 2% of the population is Afro-descendant, that is, 2,576,213 Afro-descendant people according to statistics by INEGI-2020 (...) The main ones, by the number of their population, are the Nahuatl, who live in the central and southern areas of our country; the Mayans, belonging to the Yucatan Peninsula and the southeast of Mexico; the Zapotecs, from Oaxaca; the Mixtecs, from Oaxaca and Guerrero; the Tzotzils, from Chiapas; the Tzeltals from Chiapas; the Otomis, from the central zone; the Mazatec groups from Oaxaca and Veracruz; the Purépechas from Michoacán; the Totonacs from

Veracruz and Puebla; the Wixáricos from Nayarit, Jalisco and Durango; the Rarámuri from Chihuahua; and the list goes on."

Methodology.

This research will employ a mixed methodology to explore the dynamics between the various cultural worldviews and the current regulatory frameworks in relation to cultural rights. Through this methodology, it is hoped to contribute to knowledge about the evolution of cultural rights and their implications for public policies and social practices. The choice of a mixed methodology is justified by the complex and multifaceted nature of the object of study. By combining qualitative and quantitative approaches, it will be possible to:

Capture the diversity of experiences: The mixed methodology allows us to address the diversity of cultural worldviews and the multiple dimensions of cultural rights.

Triangulate the data: Triangulating data from different sources increases the validity and reliability of the findings.

Main Part

"The language of human rights is the new framework for the long-standing struggles of indigenous peoples for values as permanent and universal as human dignity, freedom, equality, well-being and justice. Today, this struggle is presented as a demand for the cultural rights of indigenous peoples, but it is not disconnected from other demands and claims to the dominant society and the national State. When they have achieved full citizenship, including cultural citizenship, human rights in Latin America will be effectively universal, but not before."

Stavenhagen, R. (2001, 388-389)

Figura 1 Mexico*Map of cultural diversity in Mexico. (Berenzon B. 2023).*

González Pérez L. (2018) argues that culture is the fundamental fabric that defines humanity. Being a collective and dynamic construction, culture encompasses everything we create, from material objects to abstract ideas, and allows us to make sense of the world around us. Through it, we transmit knowledge, values and ways of life from generation to generation, forging our identity and our relationship with others. Culture is not static, but constantly evolving, adapting to social and technological changes. In this sense, education and culture become powerful tools to promote equality and freedom, by providing all people with the same opportunities for development and growth. "...Mexico recognizes cultural rights in its Political Constitution. Article two of the Constitution refers to the multicultural composition of the Mexican nation, originally based on its indigenous peoples. Article three speaks about the education provided by the State, which must be democratic, and it is precisely under this concept that cultural origin is valued and that it contributes to the free appreciation of its defenders, the right to culture and access to the benefits of scientific progress..." (2018-19).

According to Velasco Gómez A. (2017), Mexico City stands as a cultural conglomerate where diverse expressions of identity converge, mainly those of indigenous and popular origin, along with cosmopolitan influences. This cultural plurality, called "deep Mexico", is manifested in a rich linguistic, gastronomic and festive diversity, rooted in ancestral traditions. However, this richness is confronted by the homogenization imposed by the "imaginary Mexico", a capitalist socio-economic model that seeks to impose a unique cultural identity. This tension between cultural diversity and imposed homogenization has generated a deep crisis in the Mexican nation-state. The author adds that the neoliberal project has exacerbated social inequalities and marginalized "deep Mexico", prioritizing the interests of capital over the needs of local communities. As a re-

sult, social cohesion has been weakened and the survival of the most vulnerable cultural identities has been put at risk. And she argues that the Constitution of Mexico City, despite recognizing cultural diversity and the rights of indigenous peoples, still does not fully integrate traditional knowledge and the collective rights of these groups into its public policies. She points out that the predominant individualistic approach in the recognition of cultural rights contrasts with the recognition of collective rights to the city. In addition, she criticizes the absence of considerations on cultural diversity in key areas such as education, justice and urban development planning. Velasco Gómez proposes that Mexico City must go beyond the formal recognition of cultural diversity and move towards an effective implementation of public policies that promote epistemic equity, respect for traditional knowledge and the full exercise of the collective rights of indigenous peoples.

Couder Cabral's (2009) text establishes a clear relationship between culture and sociopolitical context. The author argues that culture is not an isolated phenomenon, but is immersed in a specific social, political and economic framework. That is, culture develops and evolves based on the historical, economic and political conditions of a given society. Multiculturalism, according to Couder Cabral, is a concept that goes beyond the simple coexistence of different cultures. While factual multiculturalism is limited to confirming the existence of diverse cultures in the same space, normative multiculturalism focuses on the policies and norms that regulate the relations between these cultures. This last aspect is the most relevant to understanding the implications of multiculturalism in society. In addition, she warns about the limitation of using biological metaphors to understand multiculturalism. While the "ecosystem" metaphor can be useful to visualize the interaction between different cultures, it is important to remember that multiculturalism is a political and social phenomenon, not a biological one.

Cuadro comparativo 1.

Feature	Total (millions)	Percentage of total indige- nous people	Men (millions)	Women (millions)
People who self-identify as indigenous	23.2	100%	11.3	11.9
They speak indigenous language	7.1	30.8%		
They do not speak indige- nous language	16.1	69.2%		
People who speak some indigenous language	7.36	6.1% de la población total	3.58	3.78
They also speak Spanish	6.4			
They don't speak Spanish	0.866			

Linguistic and cultural diversity in Mexico according to the 2020 Census (own elaboration).

The table above presents data from the International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs (IWGIA 2023) on the 2020 Population and Housing Census, conducted by the National Institute of Statistics and Geography (INEGI), revealing a detailed picture of the linguistic and cultural diversity of Mexico. According to the data, almost a fifth of the Mexican population self-identifies as indigenous, which represents a considerable number of 23.2 million people. It is important to note that, although a large part of the indigenous population identifies as such, not all of them speak an indigenous language. In fact, the census indicates that only 30.8% of people who perceive themselves as indigenous speak an indigenous language. This suggests that indigenous identity goes beyond language, also encompassing cultural, social and ancestral aspects. On the other hand, the census also records a significant number of speakers of indigenous languages in the country. More than 7 million people reported speaking one of the 68 native languages of Mexico. However, it is important to note that the majority of these speakers also speak Spanish, reflecting a process of bilingualism and contact between languages. The census also shows a marked inequality in the geographical distribution of indigenous language speakers. Four states in the country concentrate more than half of the total number of speakers, which shows the importance of recognizing and valuing linguistic and cultural diversity in these regions.

Portilla, M. L. (2019) proposes a profound reflection on the situation of indigenous languages, particularly Nahuatl, in the face of the imminent arrival of the third millennium, establishing a clear distinction between mother tongues, which are the basis of a people's cultural identity, and learned languages. The former are compared to the backbone, as they support the deepest understanding of the world. However, their survival is threatened by various factors, such as the small number of speakers, competition from more dominant languages, and lack of use in relevant social spheres. On the other hand, he warns about the dangers of globalization for indigenous languages, the expansion of languages such as English and Spanish, as well as the acceleration of globalization processes, exert increasing pressure on native languages. He also argues that the disappearance of a language implies an irreparable loss

for humanity, since each language represents a unique way of thinking and understanding the world.

In his article, Baumann (2001) argues that multiculturalism is based on three interconnected pillars: the nation-state, ethnicity and religion.

The nation-state is a complex entity, the result of the confluence of rationalism (the search for efficiency and order) and romanticism (the appreciation of cultural identity). Historically, the nation-state emerged as a response to the needs for expansion and control, and was consolidated as the dominant political unit. However, its construction is based on an idealized vision of the nation and culture, often excluding and marginalizing minority groups.

Ethnicity, despite appearing to be a fixed and natural identity, is actually a social construction. The idea that ethnicity determines an individual's behavior or values is a fallacy. Genetics does not explain cultural differences, and ethnicity is rather a changing and contextual identity, shaped by experiences and social relationships.

Religion is another fundamental pillar of multiculturalism. While religion may seem like a fixed and absolute source of identity, Baumann argues that it is also a social and political construct. Religion is often used to justify conflict and exclusion, but it can also be a factor of social cohesion.

The author questions the idea that ethnicity and religion are fixed and natural categories, and shows how the nation-state has used these categories to build and maintain power. Baumann invites a deeper reflection on the social and political dynamics underlying multiculturalism, and proposes a more flexible and contextualized vision of identity and culture. Such diversity must consider the possibility of building a more solid cultural identity in the region taking into account the rights as citizens. The exercise of citizenship rights supposes the recognition of a certain community belonging through which the individual develops and determines himself. Pérez Gamón C. M. (2023 - 799)

A vibrant democracy thrives on the active participation of its citizens. By engaging in public affairs, citizens not only strengthen political representation, but also co-construct a more just and equitable future. It is imperative that political institutions promote mechanisms that allow all sectors of society, especially those historically marginalized, to express their opinions and

needs. Cultural diversity, as a fundamental pillar of democracy, must be recognized and valued in all public policies. *“Citizen participation is essential to strengthen political representation. An active and informed citizenry can demand accountability from its representatives, in fluence the political agenda and promote public policies that respond to their needs”* Pérez Gamón, C. M. (2024 - 59)

The Executive Director of the Institute for Public Policies on Human Rights of MERCOSUR (IPPDH), Andressa Caldas (2024), invites us to reflect on the importance of conceiving culture as a global public good, beyond a simple commodity. In this sense, she emphasizes the connection between culture and development, highlighting the value of both tangible and intangible heritage. It is essential to remember that culture, as a human right, is protected by various international instruments. She also highlights the pride that represents the Ibero-American cultural wealth and its potential to promote an emancipatory vision that respects human rights.

First Findings.

The importance of indigenous languages as cultural heritage: Indigenous languages are an invaluable treasure that reflects the cultural diversity and history of native peoples.

The need for concrete actions: the need to recognize and value linguistic diversity as part of a country's cultural heritage and to implement public policies that promote the preservation and revitalization of indigenous languages.

The empirical results reveal a complex interdependence, where cultural diversity, especially linguistic diversity, enriches the understanding and exercise of human rights. It was also observed that cultural diversity promotes new forms of citizen participation and a deeper understanding of human rights.

Within the framework of this effort to value and preserve cultural diversity, the United Nations General Assembly established the Decade of Indigenous Languages 2022-2032, and Mexico was chosen as the venue for high-level international events related to this initiative. The objective is to protect and revitalize indigenous languages, many of which are at risk of disappearing.

Conclusions.

This study emphasizes the importance of integrating cultural diversity as a fundamental element in the effective guarantee of human rights in the Mexican context, as well as examining the effectiveness of public policies implemented to promote inclusion and respect for diversity. Furthermore, this research invites us to think of multiculturalism not as a static reality, but as a dynamic and complex process, shaped by historical, social and political forces. The table and preliminary analysis can serve as a starting point for further research on the situation of indigenous peoples in Mexico.

Citizen participation is a fundamental human right that guarantees equality and inclusion. By involving all sectors of society in decision-making, respect for cultural diversity is promoted and the rule of law is strengthened. In the Mexican context, it is essential to

integrate the perspective of indigenous peoples in the formulation and implementation of public policies, in order to ensure that their rights are fully respected.

Recommendations

At the end of this research, we suggest the following recommendations:

- Guarantee the right to education in the mother tongue.
- Promote respect for cultural diversity in all areas of social life.
- Strengthen institutions that work in favor of indigenous peoples.
- Incorporate the intercultural perspective in the training of professionals from various sectors.

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